

RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	<i>Characterisation of the Performance of Compact Cherenkov Radiators+SiPMs Detector Systems</i>
Project TA identifier	<i>TA10-334</i>
General application	<i>Satellite-based Cherenkov detector for high-energy protons</i>
Type of test	<i>Proton response test</i>
Group leader, Institute	<i>Keith Ryden, Surrey Space Centre, University of Surrey</i>
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Date(s) of the experiment	<i>15/7/27-21/7/24</i>
Facility	<i>TRIUMF</i>
Amount of access granted	<i>24 hours</i>

Objectives of the experiments

The HEPI instrument is designed to monitor the flux of >300 MeV protons in the near-Earth space environment, whilst discriminating protons below this energy and the electron background. Protons of this energy are only accessible at beam facilities. The detector consists of Cherenkov radiators, coupled to photosensitive silicon photomultipliers. The beam test at TRIUMF had multiple goals:

- Characterising the response of a range of Cherenkov radiators (MgF₂, PbF₂ and fused silica) to protons beams of two energies (355 and 480 MeV)
- Characterising the response of the Cherenkov detectors, alternating the orientation of the SiPMs relative to the direction of the beam (parallel or perpendicular)
- Determining the response of the system as the beam flux approaches the intensities observed during high flux space weather events
- Qualifying the response of the detectors as the beam energy was manually attenuated. Cherenkov interactions are highly energy dependent, with each radiator material having an inherent threshold
- Testing the signal processing equipment – a standard nuclear instrumentation module data acquisition was used, alongside a custom signal processing PCB designed to be analogous to the electronics that would be used on a CubeSat platform

Experiment test report

A total of 44 beam tests were performed over the course of the three shifts at the Proton Irradiation Facility (PIF) at TRIUMF. The majority of measurements were taken over 15 minutes, with a further 10-15 minutes of changeover time required to setup the next experiment. For measurements with the same setup, this could be reduced to zero and at higher fluxes, the integration time was reduced as statistics were obtained in a shorter time. For each measurement, the SiPMs were held at 45 V.

Overall, all of the main targets established prior to the beam test were achieved. The preliminary analysis of the test will be discussed:

Background measurements

Above are the responses of a Cherenkov detector coupled with fused silica radiators. For the plot on the left, the four channels represent: CH1/CH2 the spectra from each SiPM, CH3/CH4 the spectra from each SiPM gated on coincidence of both channels “firing”. On the right, the response of a Cherenkov detector read out via a processing board designed to be analogous to the equipment used on a satellite.

The background measurements show a noise edge at low channels, and a broad muon peak at channel 150.

Cherenkov radiator response to proton beam:

Below is shown the response of a Cherenkov detector coupled with PbF₂ radiators, taken with a 480 MeV proton beam. The sharp peak at channel 150 can be seen, in the same location as the muon peak

observed as background. This is due to the Cherenkov light production mechanism, where the number of photons produced by a particle is proportional to the path length of that particle (whilst above the threshold energy) through a radiator. Both muons and protons will pass directly through the 1 cm radiators used for these detectors. Proton beam flux $650 \text{ particles s}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$.

Configuration/radiators study

As discussed in the proposal for the funding, the configuration of the detectors were investigated, specifically the orientation of the SiPMs to the path of the proton beam, and therefore the emitted photons. Also, the responses of radiators with different Cherenkov thresholds were investigated.

The plots above show the response of MgF₂, fused silica and PbF₂ radiators in both configurations – the top row of data taken with the SiPMs parallel to the beam, and the bottom row taken with the SiPMs perpendicular to the beam. It can be seen that the bottom row of peaks are at a higher channel than the top row, corresponding to more photons being collected in this configuration.

The difference in radiator response can also be observed, as the different materials have decreasing proton Cherenkov thresholds – MgF2 434 MeV, fused silica 320 MeV, PbF2 167 MeV. These measurements were taken at 10^2 - 10^3 particles $s^{-1} cm^{-2}$.

Beam flux study

Plot below shows measurements taken at 650, 1000, 4000, 7200 and 28000 counts/s at 480 MeV, taken with a PbF2 radiator in both standard and satellite-based output modes.

The area under the proton peak can be seen to increase with the beam flux, approaching the fluxes expected in the satellite application of a high energy proton detector. The noise peak can be seen to remain consistent even at the highest flux.

Varying Beam Energy

The beam energies (480 and 355 MeV) were attenuated using blocks of steel of varying thicknesses to access an energy range between 230-480 MeV. The motivation for the instrument is a detector that can detect protons >300 MeV, and discard any below this value. The threshold for Cherenkov interactions is dependent on the refractive index of a material, with a distribution defining the two regimes.

The plot below shows the response of fused silica radiators in the energy range 355-480 MeV, and PbF2 in the energy range 230-480 MeV, taken conventionally and with the satellite signal processing board.

The area under these peaks, and position of the peaks in the x-axis are shown in the below plot, compared to simulations of the detector responses:

It can be seen that the responses of the different materials follow the expected curves, with the proton peak intensity and total photons produced per interaction decreasing with beam energy. This is due to the protons losing energy as they pass through the radiators, at low beam energies this can lead to them being below the energy threshold. At energies ~200 MeV above the threshold, this effect is not strong enough to affect the total intensity of light strongly.

Further work

Further to the studies discussed in this report, the detectors response to accumulated radiation dose, discrimination of other particle species and larger configurations of radiators are being investigated.

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an 'X' next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	X
Data for Thesis	
Follow-up experiment at same facility	X
Follow-up experiment at another facility	
Other	

As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

RADNEXT acknowledgment:

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